

Isolation and Identification of Bacteria from Contaminated Milk

Hussaini Nuhu Shehu^{*1}, Jesse Jedral Titus², Bello Muhammad Mubarak², Saulawa Mahmud Abdullahi³, Mohammad Mustapha⁴, Gali Abaka Umaru³ and Sidi Shehu⁵

¹Ministry of Animal Health, Husbandry and Fisheries, Kebbi State

²Department of Veterinary Microbiology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, Nigeria

²Ministry of Animal Health and Fisheries Development, Sokoto State

³Department of Veterinary Public Health and Preventive Medicine, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Bayero University Kano, Kano State

⁴Department of Veterinary and Pest Control Services, Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security, FCT-Abuja

⁵Department of Theriogenology and Animal Production, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, Sokoto State

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The aim of this research is to isolate and identify the bacteria present in fresh cow milk in Sokoto and Kebbi state, Nigeria, associated with its spoilage. The result obtained indicates that the species isolated includes, *streptococcus pyogenes*, *klebsiella pneumoniae*, *salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, identified using biochemical test. The bacterial load were within the ranges of 2.21×10^4 at 10^{-4} (CFU/ML) to 2.45×10^3 at 10^{-3} (CFU/ML). The temperature employed was at mesophilic range of 30°C and pH was also determined at the range of (6.74) to (4.56). The presence of bacteria contaminants in this milk would necessitate suggestions related to recommend that there should be proper enlightenment of the public on food hygiene and handling through electronics and mass media, institutions of learning and public lectures. Other recommendations include the need to control bacterial contamination through education of processors on safety handling personal hygiene, and sanitary practice during processing and selling of milk.

Key words: Animals, milk, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*

INTRODUCTION

The quality of milk is influenced by different bacteria present in milk. Milk is a rich source of protein and nutrients that are needed for normal growth and development. In many homes in different geographical regions in the world, milk and milk products are being fed to infants and form a major component of breakfast for adults. Milk is obtained primarily from ruminant especially cows and goats, and it is processed either locally or in factories to derive products like powdered milk, yoghurt, and cheese. The nutrient composition of raw milk is excellent and is thus favorable for Bacterial growth (Scarpa and Chilton, 1978).

The nutrient present is also adequate for the growth of various pathogens. Results of extensive investigation over many years have proved that both human and animal diseases are often spread by milk and milk products. The infectious agents most commonly isolated from contaminated milk includes, *campylobacter spp.*, *salmonella spp.*, *Escherichia coli*, *listeria monocytogenes* and *cryptosporidium parvum* (Adak *et al.*, 2002). Other organisms commonly isolated from milk include *staphylococci*, *streptococci*, *micrococci*, *corynebacterium bovis*, *mycobacterium spp*, *coxiella burnettii*, and coliform Bacteria (Honkanen-Buzalski, 1982). No Bacterial flora however, can be said to be a resident of milk and as such, the milk secreted into the udder of a healthy cow is probably sterile. The presence however, of microorganisms in milk can be as a result of

*Corresponding author's e-mail: nuhusaini084@gmail.com

contamination (Adams and Moses 1999). Faecal contamination is the most likely route of pathogen introduction into raw milk (Uraih and Izuagbe, 1990).

Domestication of animals for livestock has played a key role in the development of human civilizations. The cow has now become the main dairy animal associated with milk, with the term "milk" being almost synonymous with cow milk in most people's minds. However, milk from a range of other animal species is also consumed and will therefore be covered in this chapter. The demand for milk in developing countries is expected to increase by 25% by 2025 (FOA, 2008). Small-scale livestock holders supply the vast majority of this milk, and dairy animals provide household food security and a means of fast returns for them. About 180-200 million people belong to pastoral societies that raise livestock using natural rangelands as the main forage (Degen, 2007). These rangelands are in deserts, mountains and steppes- land that cannot be cultivated or used for agricultural purposes- and cover almost 25% of the world's land surface (Degen, 2007).

Pastoralists traditionally keep more than one species of livestock in order to make the most of the rangelands, as some species are mainly grazers (as sheep and cattle), while others are better browsers (as goats and camels). Diversifying in this manner also reduces risk from diseases or extreme environmental conditions (Degen, 2007). The majority of papers published on milk composition relate to fat and fatty acids (FA) profiles. Milk protein is also well covered, total protein content being one of the main quality criteria applied to milk. Payment is made to producers in many countries where milk is priced according to composition (others being fat and solids-non-fat) (FAO, 2004).

The composition of milk from minor dairy animals (animals other than cows, buffalo, goats and sheep, which contribute 0.2% of world milk production) has so far received little research attention. This is unfortunate, as some of them (donkey, reindeer, yak, camels, moose, musk, ox, ilama, alpaca, and mithun) are underutilized, that is, "species with underexploited potential for contributing to food security, health and nutrition, income generation, and environmental services" (FAO, 2008). Knowledge of difference in nutrient in milk from various species facilitates development of products for consumers with specific needs, such as substitutes for cow milk for people with cow milk allergy, and milk formulated for the rehabilitation of malnourished individuals and other nutritionally vulnerable groups (Park and Haenlein, 2006; Suutari *et al.* 2006).

In the future, the composition of milk could be tailored to meet demand within each national economy: for example, the American and Canadian markets have an oversupply of lactose, which is disposed of for minimal returns, while the British market has an unmet demand for fat and oversupply of protein. Specific industrial demands could also be met, such as milk with high casein content

for the cheese industry (Karatzas and Turner, 1997).

The aim of this research is to isolate and identify the Bacteria present in fresh cow milk associated with its spoilage. While the objectives are to isolate and identify Bacteria associated with spoilage of raw milk and to evaluate the bacterial frequency and percentage of occurrences from the species isolated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Wide mouth container which is sterile, petri dishes, pipettes, measuring cylinder, test tube, conical flask, bent glass rod, wire loop, PH meter, distilled water, are the materials that were used. The milk sample was collected from Sidi Farms in Sokoto metropolis. Only one sample was collected directly from the cows' udder. Raw milk sample was collected in a sterile wide mouth container. It was then taken to the laboratory with minimal delay to be processed. (Oyeleke and Manga, 2008).

Preparation of Reagents

All reagents was from BDH chemicals and May and Baker. 10% FeCl₃, sulphanilic acid in 5N acetic acid, alpha-naphthylamine in 5N acetic acid, KOVACS reagents, alpha-naphthol in ethanol, 10% HCL, Methyle red reagent, 40% KOH, and gram staining reagents was used. (Oyeleke and Manga, 2008).

Media Preparation

All media was weighed aseptically and was dissolved in appropriate and measured volume of water. It was then prepared according to manufacturer's instructions and was autoclaved at 121°C for 15min. (Oyeleke and Manga, 2008)

Sample Preparation

Serial Dilution

One (1) ml of raw milk was transferred aseptically into 9ml of sterile distilled water. It was then mixed thoroughly using a pipette. The procedure was repeated until a 10³ dilution was obtained. This procedure was carried out 3 times, immediately after collecting sample while it was fresh, after 24hrs and after 48hrs. (Cheesbrough, 2006).

Bacterial Culturing

A sterile bent glass rod will be used; 1ml of 10⁻³ and 10⁻⁴ dilution of milk sample was spread on nutrient agar and was incubated at 44.5°C for 24-48 hrs. All the plates were in duplicate. After the incubation period, the colonies on each duplicate were ready for identification. (March and Ratnam, 1986).

Table 1: Showing Microbial Load of Fresh Milk Sample Collected.

Samples	Bacterial load 10^3	Bacterial load 10^4
Freshly collected milk sample	1.48×10^3	1.34×10^4
Milk sample after 24hrs	2.93×10^3	2.62×10^4
Milk sample after 48hrs	2.95×10^3	2.66×10^4

KEY: CFU = colony forming unit.

Table 2: Showing Mean Microbial Load of Fresh Milk Sample Collected.

Sample(S _i)	10^3 (CFU)	10^4 (CFU)
i. Freshly collected milk sample	1.48	1.34
ii. Milk sample after 24hrs	2.93	2.62
iii. Milk sample after 48hrs	2.95	2.66

KEY: CFU = colony forming unit.

Mean Microbial Load of Fresh Sample Collected (\bar{x}) = $\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n S_i}{n}$

At 10^3 , Mean (\bar{x}) = $\frac{1.48+2.93+2.95}{3} = 2.45 \times 10^3$ CFU

At 10^4 , Mean (\bar{x}) = $\frac{1.34+2.62+2.66}{3} = 2.21 \times 10^4$ CFU

Enumeration of Bacteria

Discreet colonies from the plate above was picked using a flame and cool wire loop, and was streaked for isolation on eosin methylene blue agar then incubated at 44.5°C for 24-48hrs (Oyeleke and Manga, 2008). All the characteristics colonies with green metallic sheen, dark centers, and also pink colonies with black centers was picked for gram staining and was also transferred onto nutrient agar slant and stored properly for biochemical test.

Gram Staining and Microscopy

A smear of each colony was made on clean grease free glass slide. It was then flooded with crystal violet, the primary stain for 60sec and rinsed off with water, decolourisation was done with alcohol which was carefully carried out before the slide was flooded with saffranin, stained for another 60sec, then it was now finally rinsed off using a slow running tap water, after which all slide were air dried. A drop of immersion oil was used to enhance view under Objectives $\times 100$ under the microscope for identification (Cheesbrough, 2006).

BIOCHEMICAL TEST

The Biochemical test carried out on the isolate were: Indole test, Methylene red-vogesproskauer test, Simpson's citrate utilization test, urease test, Motility test, and triple sugar ion test (Oyeleke and Manga, 2008).

Indole Test

Isolate was inoculated and was dispersed into 5ml of peptone water in bijoux bottle using sterile wire loop. It was then incubated at 37°C for 24hrs. Thereafter, 3 drops

of Kovacs indole reagents was added. Development of a red colour in the reagent layer above the broth will indicate a positive reaction (Oyeleke and Manga, 2008).

Methyl Red Test

Isolate was inoculated into 5ml of freshly prepared MR-VP broth and incubated for 48hrs at 35°C. 1ml of the broth was transferred into a small test tube and 3 drops of Methylene red reagent was added. Development of red colour indicated a positive result for MR test while a yellow colour indicated a negative test (Oyeleke and Manga, 2008).

Vogesproskauer Test

To the rest of the broth gotten from above, 15 drops of 5% of alpha-naphthol in ethanol followed by 5 drops of 40% KOH was added, shaken, capped loosely and placed in a sloping position. Development of red colour within an hour indicated a positive test result while no colour indicated a negative VP test (Oyeleke and Manga, 2008).

Simpson's Citrate Utilisation

Each isolate (from the MR-VP broth) will be inoculated at 37°C for 48hrs. Development of a deep blue colour indicated a positive test result while a green colour (neutral colour of the medium) indicated a negative test. (Cheesbrough, 2006).

Urease Test

Each isolate was inoculated into a urea agar slant in a bijoux bottle was incubated at 37°C for 48hrs. Development of red colour indicated a positive reaction.

Table 3: Showing Morphological Characteristics of Bacteria Isolated from Milk for sample that was freshly collected:

SAMPLES	Morphological Characteristics
1st 10 ⁻³ (1)	Gram -ve rods in chains
1st 10 ⁻³ (2)	Gram +ve cocci in chains
1st 10 ⁻⁴ (1)	Gram -ve rods in chains
1st 10 ⁻⁴ (2)	Gram -ve rods in chains

KEYS: 1st 10⁻³(1 and 2)= first and second duplicate of serial dilution at 10⁻³(CFU/ml)
 1st 10⁻⁴(1 and 2)= first and second duplicate of serial dilution at 10⁻⁴(CFU/ml)

Table 4: Showing Morphological Characteristics of Bacteria Isolated from Milk Sample after 24 hrs:

SAMPLES	Morphological Characteristics
2nd 10 ⁻³ (1)	Gram -ve rods in chains
2nd 10 ⁻³ (2)	Gram -ve rods in chains
2nd 10 ⁻⁴ (1)	Gram -ve rods in chains
2nd 10 ⁻⁴ (2)	Gram -ve rods in chains

KEYS: 1st 10⁻³(1 and 2) = first and second duplicate of serial dilution at 10⁻³(CFU/ml); 1st 10⁻⁴(1 and 2) = first and second duplicate of serial dilution at 10⁻⁴(CFU/ml)

Table 5: Showing Morphological Characteristics of Bacteria Isolated from Milk Sample after 48hrs:

SAMPLES	Morphological Characteristics
1st 10 ⁻³ (1)	Gram-ve rods in chains
1st 10 ⁻³ (2)	Gram-ve rods in chains
2nd 10 ⁻⁴ (1)	Gram +ve cocci in chains
2nd 10 ⁻⁴ (2)	Gram-ve rods in chains

KEYS: 1st 10⁻³(1 and 2) = first and second duplicate of serial dilution at 10⁻³(CFU/ml)
 1st 10⁻⁴(1 and 2) = first and second duplicate of serial dilution at 10⁻⁴(CFU/ml)

Table 6: Showing pH Scale of Samples Collected

Sample	Temperature	pH scale
Freshly collected milk sample	30°C	6.74
Milk sample after 24hrs	30°C	4.88
Milk sample after 48hrs	30°C	4.56

No red colour indicated a negative Urease test (Oyeleke and Manga, 2008).

Motility Test

Each isolate was inoculated into a motility medium by making a fine stab with a sterile needle of 1-2cm short of the bottom of the tube. It was incubated at 35°C for 24hrs. Line of inoculation was examined to see if the medium was cleared of motile and non-motile Bacterial organisms (Oyeleke and Manga, 2008).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results in Table 4.1 shows the microbial load of the raw

milk sample collected. With the sample kept for 48hrs having the highest microbial load (2.95×10^{-3}) at 10⁻³ CFU. However, its fresh sample had the lowest count (1.48×10^{-3}) at 10⁻³ CFU. At 10⁻⁴, the highest count was sample kept for 48hrs (2.66×10^{-4}) while the lowest count was gotten from fresh sample (1.34×10^{-4}). Table 4.2 shows the mean microbial counts from the raw milk sample collected. Sample having the highest mean count was 2.45×10^{-3} at 10⁻³ while sample having the lowest mean count was 2.21×10^{-4} at 10⁻⁴.

Table 4.3 shows the Morphological characteristics of Bacteria isolated from the raw milk sample collected. All were gram -ve rods except for 2 isolate that showed gram +ve cocci. Table 4.4 shows the P.H scale of samples which were taken before serial dilution of milk sample. Each sample was stored at 30°C using incubator.

Table 7: Results for Biochemical Characterization

Sample	Gram Reaction	Glucose	Lactose	Sucrose	Citrate	Indole	Motility	Gas	H ₂ S	MR	VP	Urease	Isolates
1 st 10 ⁻³	Gram negative Rod	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>
1 st 10 ⁻³	Gram positive Cocci	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>
1 st 10 ⁻⁴	Gram positive Cocci	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>
1 st 10 ⁻⁴	Gram negative rod	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>
2 nd 10 ⁻³	Gram negative Rod	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>
2 nd 10 ⁻³	Gram negative rod	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>
2 nd 10 ⁻⁴	Gram negative rod	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>
2 nd 10 ⁻⁴	Gram negative rod	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>
3 rd 10 ⁻³	Gram negative rod	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
3 rd 10 ⁻³	Gram negative rod	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>
3 rd 10 ⁻⁴	Gram positive cocci	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>
3 rd 10 ⁻⁴	Gram negative rod	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>

Keys: += Present, - =absent, 1st 10⁻³(1 and 2) = first and second duplicate of serial dilution at 10⁻³(CFU/ml)
 1st 10⁻⁴(1 and 2) = first and second duplicate of serial dilution at 10⁻⁴(CFU/ml)

Sample that was kept for 48hrs shows that it was more acidic in nature with the scale of 4.56 while fresh milk sample was within normal range with the scale of 6.74. Table 4.5 shows the biochemical characterization of Bacteria isolated from the raw milk sample collected. It was observed that there was a high occurrence of *klebsiella pneumoniae*.

$$\text{Percentage} = \frac{\text{number}}{\text{total number}} \times 100$$

Milk is a rich source of protein and nutrients that are needed for normal growth and development. In many homes in different geographical regions of the world, milk and milk products are fed to infants and forms a major component of breakfast

for adults. In table 4.2, it shows that the freshly isolated milk had the highest microbial load within the range of $1.48 \times 10^3 - 2.95 \times 10^3$ for dilution of 10⁻³ (CFU/ML) and $1.34 \times 10^4 - 2.66 \times 10^4$ for the dilution of 10⁻⁴ (CFU/ML).

In table 4.6, it shows a pH scale of sample that was taken when it was freshly collected and had a pH of 6.7

subsequently, pH of sample was checked after 24 hours and 48 hours, ranging from 4.8 – 4.5. All samples were kept in a room temperature of 30°C. This shows that raw milk tends to get more acidic without being properly preserved. From the results obtained from this study, table 4.7 shows that *Klebsiella pneumonia* and *Salmonella typhi* were the two major isolated and identified bacteria species, then *Streptococcus pyogenes* and *Escherichia coli*.

According to Sani Yusuf Hamza with admission number (0911307024), from his work “isolation and characterization of e.coli in milk and milk products”, he got only one isolate of e. coli from raw milk sample which agrees with my biochemical results of table 4.7, showing only 1 isolate of *E. coli*.

Milk, either raw or processed, is a well known vehicle of a number of human pathogens (Jay, 2000; Hitchens *et al.*, 1992). Milk and milk products have therefore been implicated in illnesses caused by contaminating pathogens. (Karmali, 1989). In countries where food borne illnesses are investigated and documented, the relative importance of pathogens like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella spp*, *Campylobacter spp*, *Listeria spp* in milk – borne infections is well known.

CONCLUSION

The result obtained indicates that the species isolated includes, *streptococcus pyogenes*, *klebsiella pneumoniae*, *salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, identified using biochemical test. The bacterial load were within the ranges of 2.21×10^4 at 10^{-4} (CFU/ML) to 2.45×10^3 at 10^{-3} (CFU/ML). The temperature employed was at mesophilic range of 30°C and pH was also determined at the range of (6.74) to (4.56).

RECOMENDATION

The presence of bacteria contaminants in this milk would necessitate the following suggestions;

- 1.1 recommend that there should be proper enlightenment of the public on food hygiene and handling through electronics and mass media, institutions of learning and public lectures.
- 2.1 recommend the need to control bacterial contamination through education of processors on safety handling personal hygiene, and sanitary practice during processing and selling of milk.

REFERENCES

Adak, G., Long, S. M. and O'Brien, S. J. (2002). *Trends in indigenous food borne disease and death*, England and Wales: 1992-2000. Gut51:832-841.

Adams, M. R. and Moss, M. O. (1999). *Food microbiology*. The Royal

Society of Chemistry, Nigeria. 133-104, 181-186

Anonymous. An assessment of the effects of pasteurization on claimed nutrition and health benefits of raw milk. MPI Technical Paper No. 2014/13.

Carter, G. R. and Cole, J.R. (1990). *Diagnostic procedures in Veterinary Bacteriology and Mycology* New York: Academic press pp 620-624.

Cheesbrough, M. (2006). *District laboratory practical in tropical countries*. Part 2 Cambridge university press, United Kingdom. 45-49

Degen, A. A. (2007). *Sheep and goat milk in pastoral societies*. Small ruminant Res., 68(1-2): 7-19.

Doyle MP, Beuchat LR, Montville TJ: *Food Microbiology: Fundamentals and Frontiers*. 2001, USA: ASM Press, 111-122. 2

Elwood, P.C., Pickering, J.E., Givens, D. I. and Gallacher, J. E. (2010). *The consumption of milk and dairy foods and the incidence of vascular disease and diabetes: an overview of the evidence*. Lipids, 45(10): 925-939.

FAO (2004). *Milk producer group resource book: a practical guide to assist milk producer groups*, by Jurjen Draaijer. Rome. Available at <http://www.karmayog.org/redirect/stred.asp?docId=21604>. Accessed 21 September 2016

FAO (2008a). *Milk and dairy product (web page)*. Animal production and health division, FAO, Rome, Available at <http://www.fao.org/ag/aq/info/themes/en/dairy/home.html>.

FAO (2008b). *Expert consultation on nutrition indicators for biodiversity 1, food composition*. Rome. Available at <ftp://ftp.fao.org/docrep/fao/010/a1582e/a1582e00.pdf>.

FAO and WHO (2004). *Code of hygienic practice for milk and milk products*. Codex Alimentarius. CAC/RCP 57-2004. Rome. Available at http://www.codexalimentarius.org/downloads/standards/10087/CXP_057e.pdf. accessed 22 September 2016

German, J. B., Gibson, R. A., Krauss, R. M., Nestel, P., Lamarque, B., Van Staveren, W. Z., Steijns, J. M., De Groot, L. C., Lock, A. L. and Destailats, F. (2009). *A reappraisal of the impact of dairy foods and milk fat on cardiovascular disease risk*. *European Journal of Nutrition*, 48: 191-203.

Givens, D. I (2010). *Milk and meat in our diet: good or bad for health?* *Animal*, 4(12): 941-1952

Givens, I. and Gibbs, R. A. (2008). *Current intakes of EPA and DHA in European population and the potential of animal-derived foods to increase them*. *Proc. Nutritional Society*, 67(3):273-280.

Honkanen-Buzalski, T. H. (1982). *Protein transfer between blood and milk as a maker of bovine mastitis with special reference to serum albumin, antitrypsin and secretory immunoglobulin*. *Proceedings of symposium on mastitis control and hygienic production of milk*, Egpo, Finland.18-22

Ihekoronye, Alard Ngoddy P.O. (1985). *Integrated food Science and technology for the tropics*. Macmillan. 343-351.

Karatzas, C. N. and Turner, J.D. (1997). *Towards altering milk composition by genetic manipulation: current status and challenges*. *Journal of Dairy Sciences*, 80(9): 2225-2232

Kleler, G (1974) *The Bacterial Flora in Aseptically Drawn milk*. *Milk Dairy Journal*. 28 (304), 220-237.

Lendenbach LH, Marshal RT: *Microbiological Spoilage of Dairy Products*, Compendium of the Microbiology of Spoilage of Foods and Beverages, Food Microbiology and Food Safety 2009, USA: Springer Science and Business media, 87-89.

March, S. B. and Ratnams, S. (1986). *Sorbitol - - MacConkey medium for detection of Escherichia coli. O517:H7 associated with haemorrhagic colitis*. *Journal of clinical microbiology*, 23: 869-872.

Mozaffarian, D. (2011). *The great fat debate: taking the focus off saturated fat*. *Journal of American Dietary Association*, 111(5): 665-666

Nelson, J.A. and Trouts G.M. (1982). *Judging Dairy Products 4th Edition*. The Olsen PP 63-73

Nnochiri, E (1975) *Medical Microbiology in the Tropic 1st Edition*. London Oxford University Press.

Oyeleke, S. B. and Manga, B. S. (2008). *Essentials of laboratory practicals in microbiology*, Best Publishers Minna. 36-65

Park, Y. W. and Haenlein, G. F. W., eds. (2002). *Handbook of milk of non-bovine mammals*. Ames, IA, USA, Blackwell Publishing Professional.

- Scarpa, L. S. and Chilton, H. K. (1978). *Source book of food and nutrition. Marquis academic media*, Chicago United States of America. 32-35
- Suntari, T. J., Vakonen, K. H., Karttunen, T. J., Ehn, B. M., Ekstrand, B., Bengtsson, U., Virtanen, V., Nieminen, M., and Kokkonen, J. (2006). *IgE cross reactivity between reindeer and bovine milk beta-lactoglobulins in cow's milk allergic patients. Journal of investing Allergy and Clinical Immunology*, 16(5): 296-302.
- Table for percentage of nutrients in milk. (2005-2010) Available at <http://www.biotechlearn.org.nz>
- Teka G. Food Hygiene Principles and Food Borne Disease Control with special reference to Ethiopia.1997, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia: Faculty of Medicine, Department of Community Health, Addis Ababa University, 73-86. 1
- Tholstrup, T (2006). *Dairy products and cardiovascular disease. Current Opinion in Lipidology*, 17: 1-10
- Uraih, N. and Izuagbe, Y. (1990). *Public Health Food and Industrial Microbiology*, Uniben Press Ltd, Benin, Nigeria.49-57
- Williams, A. P., Bishop D. R Cookburn and Scott K. J. (1976). *Composition of Dairy Research*. 42: 325-329.